

INTRODUCTION

Determining the effectiveness of commercial bank branches is particularly important. Approaches to analyzing a commercial bank's financial and economic activities are methodologically diverse and variable, yet no sufficiently developed, clearly structured, unified system for evaluating the effectiveness of a bank branch exists. As a rule, efficiency is determined in terms of the bank as a whole, which, from the standpoint of managing a credit institution rationally, does not provide an opportunity to identify inefficient branches promptly.

The topic is relevant, because the increasing number of commercial banks and financial institutions, as well as technological development, makes competition in the financial market increasingly fierce. Modern customers expect high-quality service and quick access to financial services. Moreover, assessing banks' effectiveness in digitalization is essential for understanding how to better integrate traditional and digital service channels. Efficiency assessment methods analyze the performance of branches, identify best practices, and help develop strategies to improve the bank's overall efficiency.

Thus, studying methods for evaluating the effectiveness of commercial bank branches is relevant as they are to be adapted to modern challenges, their competitiveness needs to increase, and their sustainable development is to be ensured.

The existing disparate theoretical and methodological approaches to assessing the effectiveness of the bank's branches are controversial and require further scientific and methodological study, which proves the high relevance and practical significance of developments in this area.

The study aims to develop a methodological approach to evaluating the effectiveness of a commercial bank branch.

LITERATURE REVIEW

E. Du considers investments in research and development as a practical method of increasing banks' competitiveness. The author created a system for evaluating the bank's effectiveness based on the Internet of Things [1].

M. West Meiers examines the experience and influence of the World Bank Group's Independent Evaluation Group (IEG) on evaluation structures and practices. The author provides information on the IEG's work on assessment methods and monitoring systems and on its role as an organizer of global initiatives related to assessment [2].

P. H. Nam et al. studied the impact of internal controls on the profitability of Vietnamese commercial banks. Their research shows that factors related to banking characteristics and macroeconomic factors such as bank size, number of years of operation, inflation, and GDP growth, affect the profitability of Vietnamese commercial banks [3].

D. P. Hoang et al. investigate the determinants of a bank's reputation in the context of Vietnam's banking sector during the COVID-19 crisis. Their results show that in addition to customers' perception of their banks' products and services, financial capabilities, satisfaction, and trust, banks' ability to provide risk management solutions to customers also has a positive impact on the bank's reputation [4].

M. C. Lopez-Penabad et al. study the impact of corporate social performance (CSP) on the bank's efficiency is analyzed. The authors' results indicate a U-shaped relationship between CSP and efficiency, which indicates that banks with high or low levels of CSP are the most effective [5].

N. S. Mahmood and E. M. Ahmed study the impact of risk management practices on financial performance in Iraqi private banks and confirm that such practices play an intermediary role in the relationship between risk-related factors and financial performance [6].

J. Nel and C. Boshoff study the mechanisms that help explain the impact of customer satisfaction with traditional banks on the intention to reject digitalization. The authors identified statistically significant indirect effects: 1) lack of perception of relative advantage, 2) lack of perception of compatibility, and 3) value barrier affecting the lack of perception of relative advantage as intermediaries [7].

According to A. M. P. Arandara and S. Takahashi, during COVID-19, the technical efficiency and overall productivity of factors decreased from 99% to 85%. The dominant factor contributing to this decline was the change in scale. The loan cancellation program adopted during the COVID-19 crisis and increased competition in the market could reduce the size of transactions, thus possibly contributing to this decrease [8].

T. Costa et al. write that banks' financial stability is traditionally assessed using accounting coefficients. According to the authors, market information can significantly improve these models' ability to predict an unfavorable banking situation. The study shows that the predictive power of market variables increased after stricter information requirements established by the Basel Accords [9].

U. A. Unwan and C. Ergenc believe that measuring and evaluating indicators determine banks' positions in the sector and are of strategic importance in managing processes for the country's economy. By measuring indicators, banks can assess the situation necessary to create a competitive advantage and interpret their potential for risk-taking [10].

C. Basdekis et al. study FinTech penetration into the Greek banking system. According to the authors' results, customers of all ages trust traditional banks more than FinTech companies, while the level of mobile transactions for each consumer depends on age and education. Security is the main factor that worries customers using financial services from FinTech companies [11].

Thus, the scientific problem of studying methods for evaluating the effectiveness of bank branches lies in the need to develop and improve strategies and approaches that allow for an adequate and comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of bank branches in a rapidly changing financial environment. At the same time, it is necessary to consider various criteria and indicators that can be used to assess the effectiveness of the bank's branches (financial, operational, qualitative, etc.). Non-material factors such as service quality, customer satisfaction, and the bank's reputation play an important role, but their assessment is complicated. In addition, the efficiency of the bank's branches may depend on external factors such as the economic situation, competition, changes in legislation, and technology. With the transition to digital technologies and online banking, traditional performance assessment methods become obsolete. Comparing the effectiveness of different banks and their branches requires considering various factors including different scopes, geographical location, and target audience.

The effectiveness of the bank as a whole and its branches has a great impact on the credit institution, as it provides an opportunity to identify weaknesses in the organization's activities and adjust them to increase efficiency in the future, as well as on current and potential bank customers seeking to minimize their risks by meeting their need for banking services and products.

Modern scientific literature offers no single approach to defining the essential and meaningful characteristics of the concept of effectiveness which is often replaced by a related concept. Notably, performance indicators are derived from metrics that reflect the interdependence and complementarity of these concepts.

This study does not focus on existing theoretical and methodological approaches to assessing the effectiveness of the bank's activities as these received sufficient development in the scientific and periodical literature [12; 13] and application in practical banking [14; 15].

This paper will adhere to the following definition: the effectiveness of a commercial bank is an economic category that characterizes the financial result achieved by the bank in the course of its activities, as well as pre-established strategic goals or guidelines that ensure its competitiveness and sustainable development [16].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials served as research in banking, finance, and economics, published in peer-reviewed journals such as The Journal of Supercomputing, SN Business & Economics, Review of Managerial Science, Journal of Financial Services Marketing, Asia-Pacific Journal of Regional Science, Journal of Banking Regulation, Computational Economics, Journal of Banking and Financial Technology, and others.

For this study, the rating assessment method (point-weight assessment) and the coefficient method are proposed from the existing techniques used in the overall evaluation of a credit institution activities. The advantages of the point-weight assessment include the complex nature of assessment procedures based on the results of evaluations for various parameters. The benefits of the coefficient method, in addition to the complex nature of the assessment based on the calculation of the developed list of coefficients, simplicity, efficiency, and retrospective nature of the evaluation, include the possibility of interpreting the assessment results, taking into account regulatory values and similar indicators of competing banks.

The modern theory of financial analysis developed a significant number of coefficients used in assessing the bank's financial and operational activities [17; 18]. Notably, a significant part of the indicators cannot be used to determine the effectiveness of the bank's branch, since accounting and analytical limitations do not allow calculations for individual indicators.

To analyze the effectiveness of the bank's branch, we propose using the following set of coefficients (indicators) that characterize, in our opinion, the key aspects of the branch's activities. These will ultimately be reduced to the Integrated Enterprise Excellence (IEE).

The coefficient of aggressiveness-caution of credit policy (K_1) characterizes the orientation of credit policy and is determined by the formula:

$$K_1 = \frac{\text{volume of loan investments}}{\text{amount of funds raised}} * 100\%$$

Suppose the ratio is more than 70%. In that case, it can be considered that the bank is pursuing an "aggressive" credit policy (the upper limit of such policy is set at 78%). If the indicator is above the upper limit, the lending activities are unjustifiably dangerous. If the ratio is less than 60%, the bank is pursuing a "cautious" credit policy (with such policy, the lower limit is set at 53%). The indicator's value below 53% means the bank may be at risk of losing profits and of incurring losses.

The next indicator characterizing the effectiveness of active operations is the profitability of the bank branch's assets (K_2):

$$K_2 = \frac{\text{interest income}}{\text{interest} - \text{bearing assets}} * 100\%$$

The growth of the dynamic indicator is a positive trend for the department; i.e., the higher the value of the indicator, the higher the profitability.

The following indicator is the share of term deposits in the total amount of liabilities (K_3):

$$K_3 = \frac{\text{term deposits}}{\text{liabilities}} * 100\%$$

The coefficient characterizes the degree of constancy and stability of the resource base. The growing share of term deposits in the total amount of liabilities of the bank's branch is assessed positively since term deposits, as the most stable component, are provided at an acceptable level and allow increasing the bank's liquidity and conducting operations to allocate resources for a longer period. The recommended share of term deposits should be at least 50%.

The next indicator of the department's performance is the efficiency coefficient for the use of attracted funds (K_4):

$$K_4 = \frac{\text{raised funds}}{\text{credit investments}} * 100\%$$

The coefficient value of 100% means the bank uses the entire volume of funds raised solely as a lending resource; the value greater than 100% indicates that the bank has the opportunity to use the funds raised not only as credit resources but also as a source of other active operations; the value less than 100% means the bank is not effectively raising funds for credit operations.

The ratio of interest income to expenses (K_5) is:

$$K_5 = \frac{\text{interest income}}{\text{interest expense}}$$

The coefficient evaluates the profitability of the bank branch's operations. The growing indicator shows an increase in operational efficiency.

The ratio of commission and interest income (K_6) is:

$$K_6 = \frac{\text{commission income}}{\text{interest income}}$$

The indicator evaluates the ratio of a bank's risk-free and risky income. The indicator growing in dynamics means a positive trend, i.e., the higher the indicator value, the better for the organization.

The cost structure indicator (K_7) is calculated using the formula:

$$K_7 = \frac{\text{administrative and management expenses}}{\text{net income}} * 100\%$$

This coefficient shows how much administrative and managerial expenses are incurred per 1 ruble of the financial result.

The cost-effectiveness coefficient (K_8) is the ratio of income and expenses:

$$K_8 = \frac{\text{total income}}{\text{total expenses}}$$

The coefficient evaluates the efficiency of the bank's branch and its ability to cover expenses with income. It must be greater than 1 – if it equals 1, the bank branch is break-even; if it is less than 1, it is unprofitable.

The following Cost Income Ratio (CIR), or operational efficiency, is an internationally recognized indicator of a bank branch's effectiveness.

This coefficient is proposed to be considered in two variations: the department's CIR and the employee's CIR.

The department's CIR (K_9) is calculated using the formula:

$$K_9 = \frac{\text{operating expenses}}{\text{operating profit}}$$

The coefficient shows which sum in rubles it took to spend within the department's work to generate 1 ruble of income. An increase in the indicator corresponds to a decline in business efficiency, whereas a decrease signifies improved efficiency. The bank is conducting unprofitable activities if the CIR indicator exceeds 100%. CIR value of up to 50% is acceptable for banking practice.

The employee's CIR (K_{10}) is defined as follows:

$$K_{10} = \frac{\text{personnel costs}}{\text{operating profit}} * 100\%$$

The coefficient shows which sum in rubles it took to spend on an employee within the department's work to generate 1 ruble of income.

To determine the IEE, the Central Bank of the Russian Federation, in Instructions No. 4336-U dated April 3, 2017, "On Assessing the economic situation of banks", proposes using the coefficient method and a scoring system.

RESULTS

Based on the results of calculating the coefficients and the values obtained, each of the proposed indicators is assigned its own score, and the weight is determined by expert analysis (the algorithm for determining the weight is presented in more detail in the instructions of the Central Bank of the Russian Federation No. 4336-U dated April 3, 2017, "On Assessing the economic situation of banks") (see Table 1).

Table 1

Point-weight assessment of the bank branch's performance indicators

Indicator name	Values			Weight
	1 point	2 points	3points	
Coefficient of "aggressiveness-caution" of credit policy, K_1	≥ 53 & < 60	≥ 60 & ≤ 78	< 53 & > 78	3
Profitability ratio of the bank branch's assets, K_2	≥ 1.4	≥ 0 & < 1.4	< 0	3
Share of term deposits in total liabilities, K_3	≥ 50 & < 75	≥ 75 & < 100	< 50	2
Efficiency coefficient for attracted funds, K_4	> 100	$= 100$	< 100	3
Ratio of interest income to expenses, K_5	≥ 1	> 0 & < 1	≤ 0	2
Ratio of commission and interest income, K_6	≥ 0.5	> 0 & < 0.5	≤ 0	2
Cost structure indicator, K_7	≤ 60	> 60 & ≤ 100	> 100	2
Cost efficiency coefficient, K_8	> 1	$= 1$	< 1	3
CIR units, K_9	> 0 & < 50	> 50 & < 100	≥ 100	3
Employee's CIR, K_{10}	> 0 & < 50	> 50 & < 100	≥ 100	2

Based on the results of assigning a score and determining the weight, the IEE indicator of the bank branch is calculated using the formula:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{10} (score_i \times weight_i) \div \sum_{i=1}^{10} weight_i$$

Table 2 shows the obtained values; the dynamics can be traced to the change in the position of the bank branch.

Table 2

Assessment of the bank's branch activities based on the IEE indicator

Period	Good	Satisfactory	Doubtful
	≥ 1 & > 2	≥ 2 & > 3	≥ 3
2021			
2022			
...			

The IEE indicator, based on a set of indicators characterizing the main aspects of the department's activities, determines the state of the bank's department as follows:

- Good – the IEE indicator is greater than or equal to 1 but less than 2; this suggests that the bank is not experiencing financial difficulties and generally demonstrates a high level of efficiency;

- Satisfactory – the IEE indicator is greater than or equal to 2 but less than 3; this applies to banks that are not currently experiencing difficulties but exhibit operational shortcomings that could develop into problems within the next 12 months;
- Doubtful – the IEE indicator is greater than or equal to 3; this category includes bank branches facing financial difficulties that may pose risks to customer interests within the year [8].

The department's changing dynamics determines the need to adjust its activities to increase efficiency.

The results were tested using the example of one of the branches of PJSC Credit Bank of Moscow to test a methodological approach: calculation of an IEE indicator of the department's performance.

The initial data for the calculation are presented in Table 3.

Table 4 shows the results of calculating the indicator value and determining the point-weight value of the bank branch's performance indicators.

Table 3

Key IEE indicators X, RUB

BCC	Indicator	01.2022	02.2022	03.2022	04.2022	05.2022	06.2022
10	ASSETS	439243609.5	556881344.7	552765478.5	652683752.5	672292862.9	701282980
20	LIABILITIES	695108987.4	686980272	731773442	762492823.2	786965244.2	841881026,8
203020	Urgent	592873426.3	604606817.8	678536306.8	704709605.8	732688007.3	771326273
15	Operating profit	2419271.977	3154628.738	7453816.145	2810651.946	2397356.045	2990587,882
151010	Interest income	3774978.9	3958846.1	5096607.1	5862212.5	6620920.1	6036542,8
151020	Interest expense	3905247.0	3621178.3	1706313.6	8884137.9	9817574.3	8824691,6
151030	Transfer income-expenses	2 074 402	1 995 914	3 769 186	5 063 896	5 113 958	4 701 702
1520	Net fee and commission income	501044.1	837853.2	252009.6	748843.2	492179.9	1109863,4
152510	Fines, penalties, and penalties received	5 922	11 622	25 325	20 218	4 017	10 911
1599	Imputed income-expenses	31 828	28 428	17002.38333	380	16 144	43 740
20	Operating expenses	2167087.41	1723741.94	1811521.77	2183826.04	1816250.98	2096106,65
2004	Administrative and business expenses	2167087.41	1723741.94	1811521.77	2183826.04	1816250.98	2096106,65
200401	Personnel costs	1083931.83	696042.14	739026.91	1040747.77	723677.28	686756,72
	Financial result	-1969107.87	-1542362.91	3756120.79	-1851909.95	-5149491.18	-1877628,78

Table 4

Determination of the point-weight value of IEE X

Indicator	UV	Indicatorvalue as of01.2022			Indicatorvalue as of02.2022			Indicatorvalue as of03.2022			Indicatorvalue as of04.2022			Indicatorvalue as of05.2022			Indicatorvalue as of06.2022		
		Point	B-Vvalue																
K ₁	3	63.2	2	6	81.1	3	9	75.5	2	6	85.6	3	9	85.4	3	9	83.3	3	9
K ₂	3	0.9	2	6	0.7	2	6	0.9	2	6	0.9	2	6	1.0	2	6	0.9	2	6
K ₃	2	85.3	2	4	88.0	2	4	92.7	2	4	92.4	2	4	93.1	2	4	91.6	2	4
K ₄	3	158.3	1	3	123.4	1	3	132.4	1	3	116.8	1	3	117.1	1	3	120.0	1	3
K ₅	2	0.97	3	6	1.09	1	2	2.99	1	2	0.66	3	6	0.67	3	6	0.68	3	6
K ₆	2	0.13	3	6	0.21	3	6	0.05	3	6	0.13	3	6	0.07	3	6	0.18	3	6
K ₇	2	-110.1	3	6	-111.8	3	6	48.2	1	2	-117.9	3	6	-35.3	3	6	-111.6	3	6
K ₈	3	1.0	2	6	1.3	1	3	2.6	1	3	1.1	1	3	1.0	2	6	1.1	1	3
K ₉	3	89.6	2	6	54.6	2	6	24.3	1	3	77.7	2	6	75.8	2	6	70.1	2	6
K ₁₀	2	44.8	1	2	22.1	1	2	9.9	1	2	37.0	1	2	30.2	1	2	23.0	1	2
	25			51			47			37			51			54			51

Next, using the IEE determining formula, we calculate:

$$\text{IEE as of 01.2022} = \sum_{i=1}^{10} (\text{point}_i \times \text{weight}_i) \div \sum_{i=1}^{10} \text{weight}_i = 51 \div 25 = 2.04$$

Table 5 shows the results obtained, and we obtain the department's final characteristic regarding the effectiveness of its activities in a specific period.

Similarly, we calculate the IEE for each period and enter the values obtained in Table 5.

Table 5

Evaluation of department activities X based on an IEE indicator

Period	Good	Satisfactory	Doubtful
	≥ 1 and < 2	≥ 2 and < 3	≥ 3
01.2022		2.04	
02.2022	1.88		
03.2022	1.48		
04.2022		2.04	
05.2022		2.16	
06.2022		2.04	

Thus, we can conclude that X has no current difficulties, but its activities have shortcomings that may turn into problems within 12 months.

The high volatility of the coefficients and indicators X is due to the prevailing operating conditions – a significant increase in deposit rates due to the rise in the key rate to 20%. Taking into account the emerging positive trends in the deposit portfolio's growth and the loan portfolio's growth, measures should be taken in the context of each indicator, which will ultimately contribute to improving the department's efficiency.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

With the transition to digital technologies and online banking, new assessment methods must be developed that take into account the specifics of both traditional and digital branches [19]. This opens up opportunities for research into integrating digital and physical service channels.

Considering changes in the banking environment and consumer preferences, new metrics and indicators for evaluating performance are needed. This may include assessing customer experience, satisfaction level, and other non-material factors [20].

In an unstable economic environment and with increasing risks associated with financial transactions, the assessment of branch effectiveness can be integrated with risk management systems [21].

With the development of big data processing and analytics technologies [22], banks can use these tools to assess the effectiveness of their branches more accurately.

Since the analyzed coefficients are, in fact, the resulting performance indicators of managers and are based on sales efficiency, any changes aimed at improving the efficiency of the department's activities will primarily be related to the adjustment (updating) of the sales plan for banking products. Therefore, it seems logical to refine the methodological approach in the future by including performance coefficients of managers in it, which, in our opinion, will allow obtaining more accurate details on the content and interdependence of the coefficients.

The presented methodological approach reveals that the proposed coefficients used to obtain an IEE of the branch's effectiveness are interrelated and confirm the actual position of the bank's branch, which enhances the reliability and objectivity of the result obtained.

The proposed approach can be applied to the practical activities of a commercial bank with branches to assess their effectiveness and, if necessary, adjust their activities.

The presented approach is the private opinion of the team of authors and does not pretend to be the absolute truth or an exhaustive solution to the problem in question. Therefore, it is proposed for discussion by the professional community and for further development.

REFERENCES

1. Du, E. (2022). Impact of bank research and development on total factor productivity and performance evaluation by RBF network. *The Journal of Supercomputing*, 78, 12070–12092. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11227-022-04358-x>
2. West Meiers, M. (2022). The Independent Evaluation Group (IEG) of the World Bank Group: Influences on Evaluation Structures and Practices Globally and in the Americas. In: Stockmann, R., Meyer, W., Szentmarjay, L. (eds) *The Institutionalisation of Evaluation in the Americas*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81139-6_15
3. Nam, P. H., Ngoc Thach, N., Van Tuan, N., Nhat, N. M., & Nhung, P. T. H. (2022). Does Internal Control Affect Bank Profitability in Vietnam? A Bayesian Approach. In: Ngoc Thach, N., Kreinovich, V., Ha, D.T., Trung, N. D. (eds) *Financial Econometrics: Bayesian Analysis, Quantum Uncertainty, and Related Topics*. ECONVN 2022. *Studies in Systems, Decision and Control*, vol 427. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98689-6_14
4. Hoang, D. P., Doan, N. T., & Nguyen, T. H. H. (2022). An expanded model of bank reputation in the context of the Covid-19 crisis: a vietnamese contribution. *SN Business & Economics*, 2, 62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43546-022-00234-1>
5. Lypez-Penabad, M. C., Iglesias-Casal, A., & Neto, J. F. S. et al. (2023). Does corporate social performance improve bank efficiency? Evidence from European banks. *Review of Managerial Science*, 17, 1399–1437. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11846-022-00579-9>
6. Mahmood, N. S., & Ahmed, E. M. (2023). Mediating effect of risk management practices in Iraqi private banks financial performance. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 28, 358–377. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-022-00155-y>
7. Nel, J., & Boshoff, C. (2023). Unraveling the link between status quo satisfaction and the rejection of digital-only banks. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 28, 189–207. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-022-00146-z>
8. Arandara, A. M. P., & Takahashi, S. (2023). Productivity analysis of Sri Lankan cooperative banks: input distance function approach. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Regional Science*, 7, 93–117. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41685-022-00260-9>
9. Costa, T., Lobro, J., & Pacheco, L. (2023). Reassessing bank monitoring models: an empirical analysis of the value of market signals in the period 2008–2020. *Journal of Banking Regulation*, 24, 206–227. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41261-022-00194-4>
10. Ünvan, Y. A., & Ergenç, C. (2022). Financial Performance Analysis with the Fuzzy COPRAS and Entropy-COPRAS Approaches. *Computational economics*, 59, 1577–

1605. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10614-021-10143-4>
11. Basdekis, C., Christopoulos, A., & Katsampoxakis, I. et al. (2022). FinTech's rapid growth and its effect on the banking sector. *Journal of Banking and Financial Technology*, 6, 159–176. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42786-022-00045-w>
 12. Neretina, E. A., & Soldatova, E. V. (2010). Modern concepts of commercial bank performance efficiency. *Finance and credit*, 13 (397), 14–22. (in Russ.)
 13. Karataeva, G. E., & Shikhveledova, D. K. (2020). Performance efficiency of commercial banks: concept and assessment methods. *Bulletin of Surgut State University*, 3, 6–16. (in Russ.)
 14. Berezovsky, S. O. (2013). Payback of an additional office: Cost/Income assessment and analysis methods. *To the head of a bank branch*, 1 (01), 97–103. (in Russ.)
 15. Dolzhenko, R. A. (2018). Assessment of the effectiveness of a bank sales office. *Economic analysis: theory and practice*, 17 (9), 1696–1706. (in Russ.)
 16. Karataeva, G. E., & Shikhveledova, D. K. (2020). Efficiency of commercial banks: concept and assessment methods. *Bulletin of Surgut State University*, 3, 6–16. (in Russ.)
 17. Vyskachkina O. A., & Dubova S. E. (2011). Methodology for assessing the efficiency of a regional bank. *News of higher educational institutions. Series: Economics, Finance and Production Management*, 2 (8), 21–27. (in Russ.)
 18. Akhmatov, H. A., & Dubova, S. E. (2012). Methodology for assessing the efficiency of a multi-branch bank. *News of higher educational institutions. Series: Economics, Finance and Production Management*, 3 (13), 3–7. (in Russ.)
 19. Calzada, J., Fageda, X., & Martınez-Santos, F. (2023). Mergers and bank branches: two decades of evidence from the USA. *Empirical Economics*, 64, 2411–2447. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-022-02307-4>
 20. Enad, O. M. A., & Gerinda, S. M. A. (2022). Enhancing financial performance of the banks: the role of customer response and operations management. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 11, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-022-00211-w>
 21. Wu, B., An, X., & Wang, C. et al. (2022). Extending UTAUT with national identity and fairness to understand user adoption of DCEP in China. *Scientific Reports*, 12, 6856. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10927-0>
 22. Song, Y., & Wu, R. (2022). The Impact of Financial Enterprises' Excessive Financialization Risk Assessment for Risk Control based on Data Mining and Machine Learning. *Computational Economics*, 60, 1245–1267. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10614-021-10135-4>
 23. Zouaoui, H., & Zoghلامي, F. (2023). What do we know about the impact of income diversification on bank performance? A systematic literature review. *Journal of Banking Regulation*, 24, 286–309. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41261-022-00201-8>

24. Durguti, E., & Gashi, E. (2022). Application of Corporate Governance Mechanisms to Protect the Value of Shareholders: Evidence of the Banking Sector in Kosovo. In: Yaseen, S. G. (eds) Digital Economy, Business Analytics, and Big Data Analytics Applications. Studies in Computational Intelligence, vol 1010. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-05258-3_44
25. Goswami, A. (2023). COVID-19: boon/disguise for Indian banks? *Journal of Banking Regulation*, 24, 381–402. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41261-022-00203-6>
26. Gan, V. B. Y. (2015). Banking Balance Sheet Channel of Systemic Risk. *Journal of Risk Analysis and Crisis Response*, 5, 16–30. <https://doi.org/10.2991/jrarc.2015.5.1.2>
27. Leite, L. (2023). Brand valuation: how convergent (or divergent) are global brand rankings and how correlated is brand value to enterprise value?. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 12, 375–389. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-022-00201-7>

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Dmitry I. Aslanov (Russia, Moscow) – Dr. Sci. (Econ.), Associate Professor, Project Manager. Moscow Credit Bank. E-mail: aslanovdi@mail.ru. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-4842-6775

Elena P. Smolina (Russia, Moscow) – Cand. Sci. (Econ.), Director. Moscow Credit Bank

Evgeny T. Antonov (Russia, Moscow) – Managing Director. Division for Development of Foreign Economic Partnerships of the Department of Settlements and International Financing of Sberbank.

Marina I. Golubova (Russia, Moscow) – Cand. Sci. (Econ.), Associate Professor of the Finance and Accounting Department. Pyatigorsk Institute (branch). FGAOU VO North Caucasus Federal University. E-mail: golubovami@mail.ru. ORCID ID: 0000-0001-6257-6927

Omer Allagabo Omer Mustafa (Sudan, Omdurman) – PhD in Economics, Assistant Professor of Economics, Banking and Finance. Sudan Academy for Banking and Financial Sciences (SABFS-Sudan). E-mail: omergabo78@sabfs.edu.sd. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1697-8877

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2023/12/01/aslanov/>

Received: Jun 13, 2023 | **Accepted:** Sep 12, 2023 | **Published:** Dec 1, 2023

Editor: Norlaile Salleh Hudin, Doctor of Philosophy (Management). Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, MALAYSIA

Copyright: © 2023 Aslanov, D., Smolina, E., Antonov, E., Golubova, M., Mustafa, O. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.